

DIFFICULTIES AND CHALLENGES IN DEVELOPING SPEAKING SKILLS

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Abstract: *Speaking is considered to be the most challenging skill to teach among the four language skills. The problem of teaching speaking and their classification is so complex to deal with, and it is very common for second language learners to have disfluency in speaking the target language, with incomplete words, hesitation, and repetition of some words while speaking. At times, students would choose to be speechless inside the class because of these problems. This article outlines some of the existing challenges in developing speaking and provides possible solutions.*

Key words: *speaking skills, challenges, difficulties, activities, interaction.*

Аннотация: *Говорение считается самым сложным навыком для обучения среди четырех языковых навыков. Проблема обучения разговорной речи и их классификации настолько сложна, что у изучающих второй язык очень часто возникают проблемы с речью на целевом языке, с неполными словами, запинками и повторением некоторых слов во время разговора. Иногда из-за этих проблем ученики предпочитали терять дар речи в классе. В этой статье описываются некоторые из существующих проблем в развитии речи и предлагаются возможные решения.*

Ключевые слова: *навыки говорения, проблемы, трудности, деятельность, взаимодействие.*

Annotatsiya: *Og'zaki nutq to'rtta til ko'nikmalari orasida o'rgatish uchun eng qiyin mahorat hisoblanadi. Nutqni o'rgatish muammosi va ularni tasniflash juda murakkab bo'lib, ikkinchi til o'rganuvchilarda so'zlashda to'liq bo'lmagan so'zlar,*

ikkilanishlar, ba'zi so'zlarni takrorlash bilan o'rganilayotgan tilda so'zlashda chalkashlik holatlari ko'p uchraydi. Ba'zida o'quvchilar bunday muammolar tufayli sinfda indamay qolishni afzal ko'rishadi. Ushbu maqolada nutqni rivojlantirishda mavjud bo'lgan ba'zi muammolar ko'rsatilgan va mumkin bo'lgan echimlar keltirilgan.

***Kalit so'zlar:** nutq qobiliyatlari, qiyinchiliklar, qiyinchiliklar, faoliyat, o'zaro ta'sir.*

Problems in speaking may be additionally aggravated by excessive use of self-monitoring processes and a tendency to formulate utterances in the native language first. These mental operations create obvious costs in terms of fluency and may lead to producing artificial discourse. Other problems that are commonly observed in the language classroom are related to individual learners' personalities and attitudes to the learning process and learning speaking in particular. From the psychological viewpoint, the problems of attention span, memory potential and psychological individual features of learners such as temperament, motivation and ability are identified. These factors have a considerable influence on learners' language acquisition development.

Learners in the classrooms of teaching English are diverse in all aspects of foreign language learning in terms of language acquisition. No every learner has the same problem of language acquisition. Speaking is a skill that needs many exercises. In EFL the time to do exercise is limited in the classroom. When the students out from the class they will use their mother language. From the fact, the teacher should choose the most suitable method in teaching speaking. Therefore, the language that teacher present, model, elicit, and treat takes on great importance.

Speaking of bases and their using for professional verbal speech growth it is important to remember that they promote the development of students' thinking as well as their language abilities through involving them into active creative process of language activity and interaction with each other [Ahmedova L.T., 2011;28.].

Children are quick-quick both to learn and to forget. Let them make mistakes but they should consolidate the topic. In dealing with errors, teachers have looked for correction techniques that, rather than simply giving students answer on a plate help them to make their own corrections. They may raise their own awareness about the language they are using: “what you tell me I forget; what I discover for myself, I remember” [Jim Scrivener, 2011;298]

According to Penny Ur, in his book ‘A course in language teaching’ describes Problems with speaking as follows:

1. Inhibition. Unlike reading, writing and listening activities, speaking requires some degree of real-time exposure to an audience. Learners are often inhibited about trying to say things in a foreign language in the classroom: worried about making mistakes, fearful of criticism or losing face, or simply shy of the attention that their speech attracts.

2. Nothing to say. Even if they are not inhibited, you often hear learners complain they cannot think of anything to say: they have no motive to express themselves beyond the guilty feeling that they should be speaking.

3. Low or uneven participation. Only one participant can talk at a time if he or she is to be heard; and in a large group this means that each one will have only very little talking time. This problem is compounded by the tendency of some learners to dominate, while others speak very little or no at all.

4. Mother – tongue use. In classes where all or a number of, the learners share the same mother tongue, they may tend to use it: because it is easier, because it feels unnatural to speak to one another in a foreign language, and because they feel less ‘exposed’ if they are speaking their mother tongue. If they are talking in small groups it can be quite difficult to get some classes – particularly the less disciplined or motivated ones – to keep to the target language.

In order to avoid or resolve these problems we have a number of methods and activities:

1. We can use group work. This increases the sheer amount of learner talk going on in a limited period of time and also lowers the inhibitions of learners who are unwilling to speak in front of the full class. It is true that group work means the teacher cannot supervise all learner speech, so that not all utterances will be correct, and learners may occasionally slip into their native language; nevertheless, even taking into account occasional mistakes and mother tongue use, the amount of time remaining for positive, useful oral practice is still likely to be far more than in the full-class set-up.

2. Base the activity on easy language. In general, the level of language needed for a discussion should be lower than that used in intensive language-learning activities in the same class: it should be easily recalled and produced by the participants, so that they can speak fluently with the minimum of hesitation. It is a good idea to teach or review essential vocabulary before the activity starts.

3. Make a careful choice of topic and task to simulate interest. On the whole, the clearer the purpose of the discussion is the more motivated participants will be.

4. Give some instruction or training in discussion skills. If the task is based on group discussion then include instructions about participation when introducing it. For example, tell learners to make sure that everyone in the group contributes to the discussion; appoint a chairperson to each group who will regulate participation.

5. Keep students speaking the target language. You might appoint one of the group as a monitor, whose job is to remind participants to use the target language, and perhaps report later to the teacher how well the group managed to keep to it. Even if there is no actual penalty attached, the very awareness that someone is monitoring such lapses helps participants to be more careful.

Harmer says that there are three main kinds of English teaching. It has been suggested that students of EFL (English as Foreign Language) tend to be learning so they can use English when travelling or to communicate with other people, from

whatever country, who also speak English. ESL (English as a Second Language) students, on the other hand, are usually living in the largest-language community. The latter may need to learn the particular language variety of that community (Scotch English, Shouter English from England, Australian English, Texan English). ESOL (English for Speakers of Other Languages) to describe both situations [Harmer J. 2007;12].

Conclusion: Every teacher should take into consideration that it is important to treat each student with respect, patience and encouragement and you will create a positive learning environment for everyone. Teachers when teaching speaking can come across some challenges related to the content of teaching, methods of teaching, approaches to error analysis in classroom, age factor in FLT. The subject matter should be specifically designed for various factors such as learner variables in terms of age, language proficiency levels, gender, personality traits and many other factors.

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